

Negative Stiffness Magnetic Torsion Springs for Wave Energy Converters

The power generation of a wave energy converter (WEC) can be improved if the power take-off (PTO) generator is operated with a negative stiffness [1, 2]. The addition of the negative stiffness can lower the overall stiffness of a WEC thereby enabling a small WEC to be tuned to resonate with the low frequency ocean waves. By arranging mechanical or pneumatic springs into a special inverted-Y angled arrangement negative stiffness can be created [3] and this approach is used by CorPower. However, magnets can also be arranged to create negative stiffness [4, 5] and while the energy density of a magnetic spring is lower the design is simpler and the magnet springs non-contact operating capability enables it to have high reliability and a long service life [4]. If over-torque a magnetic spring can pole-slip rather than catastrophically failing.

Most fixed stiffness and variable stiffness magnetic torsion springs published to-date have a non-linear stiffness characteristic, this makes controlling them difficult. This presentation will provide a summary of recently funded DOE research into a new class of adjustable stiffness magnetic torsion spring, such as shown in Fig. 1 that can create a linear stroke length with a ± 45 degrees. An example of the torque plot as a function of stroke length for the radial magnetic spring is shown in Fig. 2(a). This presentation will present the design of a new class of helical magnetic springs for WECs that can provide a stroke length of up to ± 150 degrees, an example plot of the torque vs. stroke length for a helical magnetic spring is shown in Fig. 2(b). This larger stroke length design is more suitable for WECs.

Fig. 1. An example of a variable stiffness magnetic spring, (b) shows the prototype test stand.

Fig. 3. (a) Torque vs. stroke length for radial flux magnetic spring and (b) for a new type of adjustable stiffness helical magnetic spring for ocean generators

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